

AL-Ma'moon University College

English Department

**Complex Word Stress
In English**

**Submitted by:
Shymm'a Majeed
Noor Najim**

**Supervised by:
Alhan Tariq**

2003-2004

Table of Contents

. Subjects	page number
1.Introduction	3
2.Definition of Complex Word Stress	4
3.Types of Complex Word Stress:	5
3.1.Stress Associated with Affix Word:	5
a. Stress Associated with Prefixes	6
b. Stress Associated with Suffixes :	7
1. Suffixes Carrying the Primary Stress	7
2. Suffixes that Do not Affect Stress Placement	8
3. Suffixes Influence Stress Placement	9-10
3.2.Suffixes Associated with Compound Word	11
3.3. Word-Class Pairs	12
4.Conclusion	13
References	15

1.Introduction

Complex Word Stress is the stress attached to words composed of a basic stem with the addition of suffixes, e.g., careful, or it is attached to two independent English words, i.e. compounds, e.g., ice-cream.

The aim behind learning English Complex Word Stress is that stress system is an important part of the English language. If any person does not get the stress right, his English sounds at best foreign and at the worst not understandable. This is when the foreign speakers confuse the verb anticipate. With the noun anticipation.

Thus, for those who speak English natively, they have to learn a regular way that distinguishes verbs from nouns, e.g., increase (n.) and increase (v.).

Therefore, a study is needed to go through complex word stress types; the definition; stress on compound words and words class pairs.

2. Definition of Complex Word Stress

**Complex Word Stress is of two major types: Word which is consist of a basic stem with the addition of affix, this word is called ‘Affix Word’, e.g., Careful. Besides, words which are made of two or more independent English words. These words are called ‘Compound Words’, e.g., ice-cream.
(Roach, 1981:79)**

**Complex Word is a word made up of one free morpheme and one or more bound morphemes, e.g., happiness, or two or more bound morphemes, e.g., receive, or one containing one or more free morphemes, e.g., feed back.
(Hartmann and Stork, 1972:45; Crystal, 1985:61)**

The stress attached to these words are called Complex Words Stress. (Roach, 1981:79)

3. Types of Complex Word Stress

3.1. Stress Associated with Affixes Words

Affixes are of two types in English:

**1. Prefixes which come before the stem ,e.g.,
un+pleasant will be unpleasant .**

**2. Suffixes which come after the stem ,e.g.,
good+ness will be goodness . (Roach,1981:80)**

**Affixes will have one of the possible effects on
word stress (see below):**

**1. Affix, it self, receive the primary stress, e.g.,
semicircle → semicircle / /
person+ality → personality / /**

**2. The word is stressed just as if the affix was not
there,e.g.,
pleasant / /, unpleasant / /
market / /, marketing / /.**

**3. The stress is remaining on the stem not on the
affix, but is shifted to a different syllable ,e.g.,
magnet / /, magnetic / /.**

(Ibid.)

a. Stress Associated with Prefixes

The stress in words with prefixes is governed by the same rules as those for words with out prefixes, e.g., pleasant → unpleasant . (Roach, 1981:52)

b. Stress Associated with Suffixes

1. Suffixes Carrying Primary Stress Themselves

If the stem consist of more than one syllable, the secondary stress will be on one of the syllables, but not on the last one ,e.g., Japan / ˈjæpən /, Japanese / ˌjæpəˈniːz /. (Roach, 1981:80-81)

In Japan / ˈjæpən /, the primary stress is on the last syllable ,but when the suffix carrying stress is added, the primary stress is on the suffix, and the secondary stress is placed not on the second syllable, but on the first : e.g. Japanese / ˌjæpəˈniːz /. (Ibid.)

The following examples explain the above:

1. -ain (for verbs) ,entertain / ɪnˈteɪn /
 2. -eer (for nouns),volunteer / ˌvɒlənˈtɪər /
 3. -ette (for nouns),cigarette / ˌsɪɡəˈret /
 4. -ese (for adjectives) Sudanese / ˌsʌdənˈiːz /
 5. -esque, -ique (for adjectives), picturesque / ˌpɪktʃərɪˈsk /
unique / ˈjuːnɪk /
 6. -ee refugee / ˌrefʊˈdʒiː /
- (Ibid.)

2.Suffixes that Do not Affect Stress Placement

When a suffix is added the stress falls on the root,
e.g.,fail / /, failure / /.(Hamash,1976:55)

The following examples by (Roach, 1981:81)
explain the above:

1. <u>-able</u>	<u>comfort</u> /	/,	<u>comfortable</u> /	/
2. <u>-age</u>	<u>anchor</u> /	/,	<u>anchorage</u> /	/
3. <u>-al</u>	<u>refuse</u> /	/,	<u>refusal</u> /	/
4. <u>-en</u>	<u>wide</u> /	/,	<u>widen</u> /	/
5. <u>-ful</u>	<u>wonder</u> /	/,	<u>wonderful</u> /	/
6. <u>-ing</u>	<u>amaze</u> /	/,	<u>amazing</u> /	/
7. <u>-ish</u>	<u>devil</u> /	/,	<u>devilish</u> /	/
8. <u>-like</u>	<u>bird</u> /	/,	<u>birdlike</u> /	/
9. <u>-less</u>	<u>power</u> /	/,	<u>powerless</u> /	/
10. <u>-ly</u>	<u>hurried</u> /	/,	<u>hurriedly</u> /	/
11. <u>-ment</u>	<u>punish</u> /	/,	<u>punishment</u> /	/
12. <u>-ness</u>	<u>yellow</u> /	/,	<u>yellowness</u> /	/
13. <u>-ous</u>	<u>poison</u> /	/,	<u>poisonous</u> /	/
14. <u>-fy</u>	<u>glory</u> /	/,	<u>glorify</u> /	/
15. <u>-y</u>	<u>fun</u> /	/,	<u>funny</u> /	/
16. <u>-wise</u>	<u>other</u> /	/,	<u>otherwise</u> /	/

Moreover, Qurik and Greenbaum (1973:451)
that native words and early French adoptions tend to
have the main stress on the root and keep it there,
such as,kingly, kingliness and unkingliness.

Besides, -ite leaves the place of the accent
unchanged, e.g., Trotsky ~ Trotskite.

3.Suffixes Influence Stress Placement

Words like Calvinism, Piatonism, Imperialism, and Socialism are often derived from the name of the Founder or derived from adjectives ending with -ial. Besides, words like Toryism, Whiggism, Jiniosm and Classicism accept the -its , as in, dentist .

According to Roach (1981:80), if the suffix is added to these words , the stress is shifted in the stem, e.g., Catholicism from Catholic.

Zandvoort (1967:310-11) finds that words which end in -ity are not considered as English words. The suffix -ity is used to derived nouns from some adjectives ending in -able or -ible , -al and -iccal, as in,
readable ➔ readability ;
visible ➔ visibility;
sentimental ➔ sentimentality;
historic ➔ historicity and comical ➔ comicality.
The reason is due to words that differences in placing the stress in the stem and the affixed word.

The same applies to words that are spelt with -able as these are not derived from modern English words. This is shown by the difference of stress, and vowel sounds , e.g., admire ➔ admirable;
revoke ➔ irrevocable . (Ibid.)

The same is true with the change of spelling and Pronunciation and the shifting of stress, as in ,
Suburban / / from suburb / /. (Ibid.)

The following examples by Roberts (1962:168)

containing the same idea:

operate → operation and elaborate → elaboration.

Qurik and Greenbaum (1973:451) state that in words which are based on classical language, the place of the stress varies according to the affixation, transport, transportable and transportation.

All abstract nouns ending in -ion are stressed on the part preceding, e.g., classify → classification; formalize → formalization. Some penultimate examples with adjectival (-ic) follows this rule, as in, phoneme → phonemic and economy → economic.

The same rule applies to antepenultimate with nouns ending with -ity and nominal or adjectival -ion, which are shown in the following examples: library → librarian and curious → curiosity. (Ibid.)

1.-graphy	<u>photo</u> /	/, <u>photography</u> /	/
2. -ous	<u>advantage</u> /	/, <u>advantageous</u> /	/
3. -ial	<u>proverb</u> /	/, <u>proverbial</u> /	/
4. -ic	<u>climate</u> /	/, <u>climatic</u> /	/
5. -ion	<u>perfect</u> /	/, <u>perfection</u> /	/
6. -ious	<u>injure</u> /	/, <u>injurious</u> /	/
7. -ity	<u>tranquil</u> /	/, <u>tranquility</u> /	/
8. -ive	<u>reflex</u> /	/, <u>reflexive</u> /	/

(Roach, 1981:82)

3.2. Stress Associated with Compound Words

Compound Words have the primary stress on the first word, as in, green-house. However, there are some cases where the two primary stress can be found in the word well-bred.

Compound nouns have a primary stress on the first syllable, and a secondary stress on the second syllable. For nouns, the first part of the noun takes the stress ,as in, apartment house; and in two- word adverb takes the stress,e.g.,go up.

(Hamash, 1976:54,55,57)

Roberts (1956:228-29) finds that stress can be used to distinguish the nouns, adjectives and verbs in any given spoken sentence. In “He’s a sweet sale man”,one can tell whether the sale man is sweet or he sells candy . this ambiguity appears in written form only.In speech , sweet will have a secondary stress if it is adjective, or takes a primary stress if it is a noun, such as,

-He’s a sweet sales man (the sales man is sweet)

-He’s a sweet sales man (the sells Candy)

Besides, the sentence “That’s s smoking room”, is ambiguous in writing. It may mean a room where smoking is permitted, or a room that is on fire.

By using stress, these two meanings would be clearly separated in speech. In sentence with the first meaning ,the primary stress should go on smoking. For the second sentence, with second meaning the primary stress should go on room. (Ibid.)

3.3. Word- Class Pairs

There are many dozen pairs of two syllable words with similar spelling, but they differ from each other in stress placement according to word class, i.e. nouns ,verb or adjectives .

In a pair of prefix+stem words, the stress will be on the second part if it is a verb; but on the first part if it is a noun or adjective, e.g., rebel / / (n.), rebel / / (v.), present (adj.),present (v.) .
(Roach, 1981:84)

Roberts (1956:228) states that when the word subject is a noun ,sub will be pronounced louder than ject, as in, “What is the subject ?”. But if the word subject is a verb, ject will be pronounced louder,as in, “Well subject him to an examination”.

The same rule of contrast applies to increase as a noun , and increase as a verb .
(Ibid.)

4.Conclusion

1. The importance of learning complex word stress is to

know how the meaning and pronunciation of complex words are changed when they receive the stress ,e.g., rebel with stress , the word could be a noun, or rebel (a verb) by changing the position of the stress.

When the word is pronounced in a correct way with its right stress, this helps to speak English language just like the native speakers of this language.

2. Complex word stress is the stress that is placed on complex word, i.e. words composed of more than grammatical unit. It can be composed of stem+affix,e.g., careful , or compound words ,e.g., white-house.

3. Affixes have three effects on word stress:

One. The stem receive the stress , personality.

b.The stress is shifted in stem to another syllable, magnetic.

c.The word is stressed as if it is not affixed , un important.

4. Stress differences are considered to be phonological

and syntactic , as the difference in the stress placement results in different parts of speech,e.g., subject (n.),and subject (v.).The stress is to be placed on the first syllable of the noun , and on the second syllable of the verb .

NOTES

- (1) **penultimate:**The syllable that occurs
before
the last syllable of the word.
(Hornby, 1974:621)
- (2) **atepenultimate:**The syllable that
occurs after
the last syllable of the word.
(Ibid.)

References

Crystal, D. (1985). A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics. London: Basil Black Well.

Hartmann, R.R.K. and F.C. Stork (1972). Dictionary of Language and Linguistics. London: Applied Science Publishers.

Hamash, k. (1976). A Course in Modern English Grammar. Baghdad: The Institute for the Development of English Language Teaching.

Roberts (1956). Patterns of English. New York: Harcourt Brace and World.

..... (1962). English Sentences. New York: Harcourt Brace and World.

Roach (1981). Better English of Pronunciation. London: Longman.

Quirk, R. and S. Greenbaum (1973). A University Grammar of English. London: Longman.

Zandvoort, R.W. (1967). A Hrd Book of English Grammar. London: Longman.

A.S., Hornby. (1974). Oxford Advanced Learner's

**Dictionary of Current English. Great Britain:
University Printing House.**